

Information sheet 1.13

Crop rotation, associations and density, weed/volunteer control

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment

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A. Description of the RRO

Crop rotation, associations and density, weed / volunteer control can be seen as good farm practices used with some consideration for pest management, as part of general cultural control measures described by All, 1999. In general those RROs are used to prevent problems related to pests and are usually applied in various combinations to make the habitat less favourable for pests

Here are described measures related (1) to allocation of crops to field (multi-crop, diversity cropping) and (2) to control of weeds and volunteers as hosts of pests.

- **Crop rotation**

The rotation of crops provides a mean of maintaining soil fertility allowing higher yields compared to continuous cultivation of the same crop. Another effect of crop rotation is its ability to prevent the build-up of pest populations (Dent, 1991). Trap crops may be used to decrease pest pressure (Timmermans BG, 2005; Dias MC et al 2012).

Generally crop rotation is most effective against pest species that have a narrow host range and limited range of dispersal. Crop rotation has been shown to be effective against the Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) and the Western Corn rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*). In Commission decision 2003/766/EC on emergency measures to prevent the spread within the Community of *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*¹ (now repealed), obligatory crop rotation was specified in the official eradication measures against this beetle:

Art. 4.2, on mandatory measures to be implemented in the focus zone of the outbreak:

«(d) in the maize fields a crop rotation takes place whereby during any period of three consecutive years maize is only grown once, or maize is not cultivated for two years after the last year of capture in the entire focus zone ».

- **Crop associations**

Practices leading to grow different crops in the same field in a specified spatial arrangement, or to mix various genotypes of a single species, or to make more diverse field margins can contribute to prevent pest establishment and can enhance pest control by natural enemies.

- **Crop density**

An excessive crop density may favour microclimates more suitable for some pests.

¹ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2003/766 of 24 October 2003 on on emergency measures to prevent the spread within the Community of *Diabrotica virgifera* Le Conte. Now repealed.

It may also make phytosanitary treatments more difficult (pesticide does not reach all leaves...) or even impossible (because machine cannot enter the plot for instance).

• **Volunteer and weed control**

Some pests may survive in the field from one growing season to the other because of volunteers that act as reservoirs. Those volunteers may either remain infested / infected, either act as hosts for pests remaining e.g. in soil or in the field margins.

Some weeds may play a similar role, acting as hosts for some pests.

Such control may be achieved with herbicides (directly when plants of concern are selectively targeted, or indirectly when those plants are killed because normal practices lead to kill them among others), by mechanical weed killing or by hand removal. To some extent, control of volunteers and weeds may also be achieved when planting crops that do not permit the growth of plants of concern.

For instance, in Commission directive 2006/63/EC amending Annexes II to VII to Council Directive 98/57/EC on the control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi et al., it is stipulated that:

4. The series of measures to be implemented by Member States within the demarcated zone(s) established under Article 5(1)(a)(iv) and (c)(iii) and referred to in Article 6(4) shall include:

4.1. In cases where places of production have been designated as contaminated under Article 5(1)(a)(ii):

(a) in a field or unit of protected crop production designated to be contaminated under Article 5(1)(a)(ii), either

(i) during at least the four growing years following the designated contamination, measures shall be taken to eliminate volunteer potato and tomato plants as well as other host plants of the organism including solanaceous weeds (...).

Table 1: Pests that can be affected by physical methods other than temperature applied on consignments or during processing.

Plant pests	RROs			Removal of volunteers and weeds
	Crop rotation	Crop associations	Crop density	
insects, mites	x	x	x	x
fungi	x	x	x	x
bacteria			x	x
nematodes	x	x	X	x
virus, virus like organisms	x		X	X

Table 2: Material that can be subjected to physical methods other than temperature on consignments or during processing.

Plants or plant parts	RROs			Removal of volunteers and weeds
	Crop rotation	Crop associations	Crop density	
plants for planting	x	x	x	x
plant material for food / feed and other uses	x	x	x	x

B. Risk factors

• **Entry**

The relevant pathways are the trade of plants or plant parts for planting, for food and feed, for other uses (ornamental uses, industrial uses...).

The use of the RROs reduces the likelihood of the association of the pest in consignments ready to be exported by acting on the pest load. It therefore reduces the global pest load of consignments.

• **Establishment**

The use of the RROs can minimise pest populations so that they are kept below the level that is required for successful establishment.

• **Spread**

The use of the RROs may reduce the probability of association of pests with consignments in a similar way as for entry.

• **Impact**

The considered RROs mainly aim to limit the probability of entry and establishment of pests. The use of the RROs in situations where the pest is already present in the PRA area may reduce the magnitude of impact. Measures may allow the pest population to be kept under a threshold leading to acceptable impact, especially when combined with other RROs.

Cultural practices are applied at place of production.

Table 3: Nodes for the application of RROs

Points where measures may be effective	On crops at place of production	Pre-harvest	Post-harvest	At import	At place of destination
crop rotation	X				
crop association	X				
crop density	X				
removal of volunteers and weeds	X				

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RROs

Other cropping practices (RRO)	Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO
Crop rotation	Need to have good knowledge of host range and biology of the pest. Dependent on survival of life stages in bare soil or on other crops. Non-host crops may have to be planted for several growing seasons depending on the survival of the pest in the soil (e.g. 2 years for <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>).
Crop associations	Need to have good knowledge of host range and biology of the pest.
Crop density	Need to have good knowledge of host range and biology of the pest.
Removal of volunteers and weeds	To be effective, removal of volunteers and weeds must be complete as possible. Operations are generally easy in young crops but become more difficult when plants are growing as volunteers and weeds are more difficult to see and to remove.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RROs

Crop rotation can only be applied for annual cropping systems and only for pests that have a restricted host range and dispersal capacities. The availability of appropriate alternative crops may be a constraint. For example, obligatory crop rotation for maize growers can be problematic in regions where maize is intensely grown for animal feed. Specialized growers may not have the suitable equipment to grow alternative crops.

A system should be in place to monitor the implementation of this RRO by growers for several growing seasons.

Crop associations often require an overall reorganisation of the system of production at farm level, with medium and long term impacts. It may imply changes in equipment and work habits. The local agri-food sector should also be able to use the production of associated crops.

Ideal crop density is not necessarily the same when considering fight against pests, technical possibilities with equipment, yield expectations and so on. A compromise may be difficult to find.

Removal of volunteers and weeds may imply changes in rotation and/or use of pesticides, that have impact on farming systems and quality of production, and may alter the acceptability of production by local markets.

Table 4: Potential limitations to the practical application of RROs.

Limits to be considered regarding applicability	RROs			Removal of volunteers and weeds
	Crop rotation	Crop associations	Crop density	
Regulatory limitations				
Technical difficulties		X	X	X
Environmental limitations				
Social or ethical aspects				
Potential side effects		X	X	
Economic considerations	X	X	X	X

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

Chemical treatments on crops are most often an alternative to crop rotation, associations and density and to removal of volunteers and weeds. Resistant or tolerant varieties are another alternative.

F. Combinations of RROs that include these RROs

All the described RROs are commonly used in association with other RROs, but on a case by case consideration.

For instance, removal of volunteers or weeds can be done specifically (workers removing volunteers by hand) or can result from other management methods (e.g. when growing wheat after potatoes, volunteers are normally killed by herbicides commonly used in wheat fields).

Crop associations are commonly combined with restriction in pesticide used and promotion of bio-control.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO.

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combinations
Crop rotation	Production place (field)	Eradication Reduction of spread Reduction of impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large host range of the pest. • Dispersal capacities of the pest which influences the size of the area where the RRO should be applied. • Availability of alternative crops. • Availability of equipment to grow alternative crops. 	With other RROs, as part of sets of integrated measures in systems approach.
Crop associations	Production place (field)	Reduction of populations, of spread, of impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in cropping system • Availability of a market for side productions 	With other RROs (e.g. biocontrol), as part of sets of integrated measures in systems approach.
Crop density	Production place (field)	Reduction of populations, of spread, of impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yield expectation • Technical feasibility 	
Removal of volunteers and weeds	Production place (field)	Eradication. Reduction of populations, of spread, of impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical possibility • Available method and resources for removal 	With other RROs (e.g. herbicides...), as part of sets of integrated measures in systems approach.

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